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ArtiSaneFood – Biopreservation and Risk Modelling
Approaches

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

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ArtiSaneFood – Biopreservation and Risk Modelling Approaches: Book of Abstracts

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Meta-Analysis on the Inhibitory Effects of Indigenous Lactic Acid Bacteria Supernatant from Dairy Origin against Foodborne Pathogens

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Abstract

Investigations have been conducted to explore the potential of lactic acid bacteria (LAB) supernatant, obtained by separating bacterial cells from liquid medium through centrifugation, as a natural preservative against foodborne pathogens, given the known antimicrobial properties of LAB. The objective of this systematic review was to evaluate the antimicrobial activity of lactic acid bacteria supernatant against three main microorganisms associated to the contamination of dairy products: *Listeria monocytogenes*, *Salmonella* Typhimurium and *Staphylococcus aureus*.

Bibliography searches were performed in PubMed, Scopus, and Web of Science databases. A total of 21 primary studies passed the selection criteria and provided 276 observations. The main outcome was the mean inhibition zone diameter in mm (ID) and its standard error (SE). Data was partitioned into smaller segments specific to each pathogen and fitted to obtain meta-analysed values for the inhibition zone, using the maximum likelihood method.

Results showed a total of 82 observations for *L. monocytogenes*, 75 for *S. Typhimurium* and 119 for *S. aureus*. The main genus of LAB obtained was *Lactobacillus* (n=207), although other genus such as *Pediococcus* (n=28), *Enterococcus* (n=21) and *Lactococcus* (n=17) were found. The highest antagonistic activity against *L. monocytogenes* was linked to LABs of the genus *Lactobacillus* (pooled ID = 17.71 mm; SE = 0.88 mm), followed by *Pediococcus* (pooled ID 15.57 mm; SE 0.38mm) and *Enterococcus* (pooled ID 12.72 mm; SE 0.69mm). *Lactococcus*' supernatant displayed the lowest antagonistic effect (pooled ID = 10.34 mm; SE = 1.01 mm). Additionally, *Lactobacillus*' supernatant was observed to be the most effective for inhibition of *S. Typhimurium* (pooled ID 15.98 mm; SE 0.71 mm) and *S. aureus* (pooled ID 16.79 mm; SE 0.91 mm), with *Lactobacillus fermentum* (n=73) and *Lactobacillus plantarum* (n=64) as the most common *Lactobacillus* species used. Finally, the results indicated that *Lactobacillus* supernatant displays strong antimicrobial activity against all three foodborne pathogens analysed. Ongoing work will provide further insight on specific indigenous dairy LAB with the highest potential inhibitory capacity against the selected pathogens.

Keywords: antagonism; biocontrol; in vitro antimicrobial capacity; inhibition diameter.

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